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Learning Through Team Centric Exercise & Key Point Pedagogy- An Effective Learning Model for Slow Learners in Social Work Higher Education Training

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Abstract

Information collected by the human mind will be correlated with the aware concepts and skills to satisfy the desired purpose. Knowledge guides to assume, use, adopt and control both physical and societal changes. Application of knowledge encourages critical or experimental understanding to constitute wisdom. The potentiality and usage of knowledge depends upon the utilization of information. Higher education institutions have to ensure transmission and dissemination of information among students who aspires to take up social work as their career. The post graduate students should be oriented towards theoretical, ideological, legal, ethical and practical implications of each subject prescribed under their curriculum. Labour Legislation is very important subject for the Human Resource and Industrial Relation specialization students, who are willing to become HR professionals in corporate sectors. The subject comprises legal intricacies' of welfare, wage, industrial relation, social security and environmental speculations for the institutionalized labour force in India hence, the subject seems to be difficult for the students who perceived their under graduation in other than English medium. The teacher should make the teaching effective and interesting by adopting innovative pedagogy to facilitate learning in this subject. 'Team Centric Exercise & Key Point Pedagogy' a new learning Model for the slow learners in social work subjects is developed and presented in this research paper, named as 'Pradeep consistent learning Model' which inter-link learning environment, pedagogy, and interest of learners thereby improve learning abilities of the average and slow learners consistently.

Keywords: Information, Knowledge, Higher Education, Labour Legislation, Legal Intricacies, Pedagogy.

1. Introduction

Paradigm shift is the transition from one system of beliefs about reality to another ^[1]. Social work education needs to shift from the curriculum ideologies to the practical need of the social work profession. Curriculum ideologies are premises of practical education, it clarifies what should be taught, for which purpose what and what is the use of teaching ^[2]. Paulo Freire ^[3] criticized the traditional 'banking' approach of teaching, where the teacher knows everything and the student knows nothing, the teacher teaches and the students are taught, the teacher becomes the depositor and the students the depository. According to him, knowledge emerges only through invention and reinvention, through the restless, impatient continuing hopeful inquiry, which ensures human beings to pursue the world through sharing experience with each other. One of the most influential proponents of the experiential or personal relevance approach has been Malcolm Knowles, who emphasized the view that adult learners need a different kind of educational approach than children. Adults do not learn for the sake of learning; they learn to be able to perform a task, to solve a problem, or live in a more satisfied way. Hence there is a need for organizing learning experiences around life situations rather than sticking on to the syllabus of study. A climate conducive to learning is important in this approach, which would be characterized by mutual respect between teacher and students, encouragement for collaboration and cooperation among students, openness and authenticity on the part of the teacher. The teacher should help to design and execute their learning plans. Initially the teacher should give a skeleton over the subject by lecture, encourage group work over the topic delivered and individual support and guidance to get deep understanding ^[2]. It is the joint responsibility of learner, teacher and community through negotiation seek empowerment. The educator should be a facilitator of learning rather transmitter of information ^[4]. In this paper we have presented a new learning Model for the slow learners in social work subjects based on 'Team Centric Exercise & Key Point Pedagogy' named as 'Pradeep consistent learning Model' which inter-link learning environment, pedagogy, and interest of learners thereby improve learning abilities of the average and slow learners consistently.

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2. New Consistant Learning Model

According to the process of liberatory education ^[12], which is dialogical, affirms the mutual and co-equal roles of teachers and learners, and therefore, appropriate for social work education and training. The dialogical approach to learning is characterized by cooperation and acceptance of inter-changeability and mutuality in the roles of teacher and learner, demanding an atmosphere of mutual acceptance and trust. In this method, all teach and all learn. Without dialogue, there is no communication, and without communication there can be no liberatory education. Team centric learning exercise & key point pedagogy model is named as 'Pradeep consistent Learning Model' developed by Mr. Pradeep after observing the learning pattern of slow learners in social work education since past 07 years. This model will inter-link learning environment, Pedagogy, and Interest of learners thereby improve learning abilities of the students average and slow learners systematically. Hence this model works in facilitating progressive learning of slow learners in the class. According to this model each class of one hour/ one and half hour duration is organized as follows:

- Each student is asked to paste a chart sheet near to his bed in his room/hostel for oriented learning.
- The planned topic for the class will be discussed/presented using *suitable teaching method* by choosing appropriate pedagogy, and learning techniques for 45 minutes.
- After teaching, all groups will be guided to simplify the taught concepts into 'key points' within 05 minutes by group exercise. This will encourage group participation and create a healthy inter group competition among the students. This would enrich analytical skills and motivates each student to listen to the lecture attentively.
- Teacher will guide the students to supplement 'key points' with innovative and easy Flowcharts, graphs, pictures, diagrams, formulas which facilitate for easy learning.
- Any 02 to 03 students are randomly picked by the teacher from any group and asked to briefly present the gist of 'Key Points' to the whole class. This briefing opportunity will make the students to be alert during the group discussion and even improves the confidence and gradually eliminates their stage fear.
- All the students are oriented to update the 'Key Points' on the chart pasted by them at their room/hostel and motivated to read every day before they go to bed. Day by day the chart will assure confidence about awareness on the subject.
- Next day the teacher conducts the 'Entry Test' in which a set of questions on the topic discussed in the previous class will be displayed on the board. While the teacher is taking attendance the student get time to memorise the concepts from the chart what he studied in the previous day and Students will be randomly picked to answer the entry test questions from each group. The students who answer the entry test will be appreciated which motivates others to improve themselves and answer in next class ^[5]. The flow chart diagram of this model is shown in Fig. 1.

3. Conceptual Basis for the Model

According to the critical pedagogical ideology, the educator is not the pre-eminent possessor of knowledge. Learners also bring their own interpretative powers to life experiences. Both are co-sharers in the creation of what is known. When no particular interpretation deserves to have a privileged status,

then the intellectual skill of critique is essential. Students must learn how to approach whatever content is presented with means for critically assessing its virtues and shortcomings. To prepare students as reflective practioners, there is a need for expanded ways for them to appreciate their own wisdom and creativity ^[6].

A. Learning Environment: The process of liberatory education, which is dialogical, affirms the mutual and co-equal roles of teachers and learners and, therefore, appropriate for social work education and training. The dialogical approach to learning is characterized by cooperation and acceptance of inter-changeability and mutuality in the roles of teacher and learner, demanding an atmosphere of mutual acceptance and trust. In this method, all teach and all learn. Without dialogue, there is no communication, and without communication there can be no liberatory education. The effective implementation and credibility of Consistent Learning Model for Social work Education depends upon creating a good learning environment which consists the following:

(1) Conditions of Learning Pedagogy: According to a Manual for Participatory Training Methods in Development ^[13], Learners should be personally involved with others in learning process. Learning climate can be created by creating sense of high values and caring approach. Their acceptance & openness makes them independent. Freedom to express their personal concerns, feelings, ideas and beliefs without hesitation & fear shall be encouraged. Performance shall be evaluated openly. Learning process shall orient on self values, beliefs, feelings etc. The atmosphere of trust helps in learning. Differences in learners should be accepted by the teacher as differences in ideas. Learning starts when error is accepted as natural in the learning process and encourage the learners to identify alternative solutions instead of stressing them to find an immediate single answer.

(2) Principles of Learning: According to Lowman ^[7] learners should be active seekers rather than passive recipients. For engaging them in learning their attention must be focused on the material of study. The Intellectual ability will influence on the speed of learning. These differences increase as the concept becomes more complex and abstract and it decreases gradually when concepts are simplified and concrete. learning efforts can be increased by rewarding them rather than punishing. Learning related concepts in a network is less difficult and permanent than isolated information. It is difficult to learn ideas which are similar without exploring the differences between them and it is easier to learn different ideas when their similarities are focused. Students learn images and words put together better if they are emotionally related. Students enter every class with positive and negative emotional attitude which affects learning or increase motivation to seek new information. Moderate level of anxiety or challenge activates most students and increases learning but excessive anxiety interferes with learning.

(3) Student Centric Teacher: According to Lowman ^[7] an intellectually excited teacher should organize contents extremely well and present in an engaging way with high energy and strong sense of dramatic approach to the students in clear language. Relationships and differences among specific concepts and applications to new situations should be highlighted. It is important that teacher appears to love presenting the materials. Teacher should follow the following

principles. Teacher should have strong interest in students as individuals and collect feedback about the study material or Teaching, acknowledge their feelings about class assignments or policy, encourages to ask questions and allow them to express personal viewpoints, Teacher communicates openly that each students understanding is important to him, encourages them to be creative and independent in dealing with the study material, Teacher should give students choices about a few decisions of much smaller consequences-choices between options that are consistent with the objectives and availability of time.

(4) Develop Critical Thinking Skill: According to Gibbs and Gambrill ^[8], critical thinking involves the purposeful evaluation of beliefs and actions depending upon reason. Critical thinking skills can be improved among students by allowing arguments for and against controversial issues presented in the class. Facilitate students in making decisions on the basis of certain assumptions. Teach documentation which supports each decisions. Encourage Self appraisal. Emphasize on truth instead of winning any argument. Appreciate students who express with their own ideas instead of students who just agree with the teacher. The assignments shall be in such a way which should guide the learners towards new things.

B. Pedagogy Used for Learning: The methodology of teaching needs to be viewed as a teaching-learning process, which is based on the ideologies, ethics, mission, objectives and the curriculum design of the discipline. Progressive learning requires knowledge as action-knowledge that is contextualized culturally and historically, and is shaped by the interaction between students, teachers and the field exposure. The goal of teacher-student interaction should be same as that of the worker-client interaction, to build resources for independent decision making. Methods in social work education and training are important to the learning process as social work practice focus towards problem-solving process. In teacher-learner transaction to give the same dynamics like worker-client training, the educator should be a facilitator of learning, rather than a transmitter of knowledge ^[4].

(1) General Orientation on Model: Pradeep Model of Consistent Learning is a new pedagogy to improve the learning capacities of average and slow learners in social work education. The method, procedure, merits and demerits of the model should be explained properly to students and motivate them to adopt and use the method and credibility of the model depends upon the orientation of the model to the students effectively by the faculty.

(2) Participatory Teaching Methodology: It is assumed that knowledge and education are never neutral and trainer's role is to help the participants understand where their own views have come from, to challenge pre-conceptions and to encourage them to consider other possibilities. It assumes that society can be transformed by the encouragement of critically conscious persons, through a process of deconstruction, reconstruction and transformation. Participants life experiences are the major source of knowledge in this method. The trainers are not teachers, but facilitators, and partners with the participants in this process of social change.

(3) General Orientation: A curriculum is defined by Ornstein, A.C. and Hunkins F.P ^[9] as a plan for action, systematically encrypted strategies to achieve pre-determined objectives.

The Teacher should give a skeleton interpretation on the subject to be taught, important chapters, concepts, objectives of learning and uses of learning the concepts to future life.

(4) Team Formation: Randomly divide the whole number of students in the class into five groups mixing Fast, average and slow learners equally considering any previous examination scores of the students. Students should sit in the formed teams for the whole semester. According to Percival and Ellington ^[10] stages of teaching-learning starts with recognition of students current knowledge level and channelizing it through participation. Learning should ensure analysis of knowledge and self learning experiences. Learning encourage participation for relating new knowledge to current information's through critical thinking. The final synthesis will lead to application.

(5) Motivation: Motivation works as an important weapon in this model. The marks for class participation will work as positive/negative motivating factor. Consistent efforts by the students can be encouraged by student centric approach by the Teacher and Appreciation of good performers by the teacher also motivates the students in using this model effectively.

(6) Leadership and Guidance: One person is appointed as 'Leader' for each group and assigned with responsibility to maintain the formed teams throughout the semester.

(7) Assessment & Appreciation: Eraut ^[11] intended planned programme of teaching should include specifications about evaluation of progress in student as this is personal interest based practice. This method is a unique method in the education system as it is self learning rather than compulsive learning and revolves around the student welfare. The Teacher shall continuously assess the class participation of each team member by maintaining proper record. The good effort and efficient performers will be appreciated in the class which motivates them to be active in the future classes.

(8) Marking Criteria: 10 Marks will be assigned for 'Class Participation' in the subject out of the total internal assessment mark allotted for that subject.

(9) Healthy Team for Healthy Competition: This method encourage participation of students in their team by creating healthy competition among them. Healthy team can be formed by unbiased team formation process by considering fast learners, average learners and slow learners.

(10) Learning Through 'Key Points': The students cannot remember the whole taught concept but important/key points in the subject need to be noted down and if students understand and remember the key points then it is very easy for the students to memorize and retrieve whenever they need it.

(11) Presentation Improves Confidence: When any one student surprisingly asked to present on the key points of the taught subject. it ensures each students to be attentive in the class as their failure to answer may affect the credibility of their team in the class.

(12) Self Learning At Home: According to Percival and Ellington ^[10] stages of teaching-learning starts with recognition of students current knowledge level and channelizing it through participation. Learning should ensure

analysis of knowledge and self learning experiences. Learning encourages participation for relating new knowledge to current information through critical thinking. The final synthesis will lead to application. In this model the learner is given freedom to quote any key points which he feels important to be remembered by using his reason and analytical thinking and update in the chart and voluntarily learner is motivated to read the information on the chart each day and try to understand the concept through key points will facilitate imprint the concepts in mind.

(13) Consistent Efforts: Heany ^[12] states that liberatory education is mutually supported learning which enables learner to make changes instead not uncritically adopting anything. When the students take up this model consistently the key points will be imprinted in their mind and slow learners gradually gain interest over the subject and leaning begins.

Fig 1: Flow chart diagram of ' Pradeep Model of Consistent Learning' - An Innovative Pedagogy for Social Work Higher Education.

4. Methodology

The research methodology adopted to carry out the study is both exploratory and purposive in nature. The descriptive and experimental research designs were applied in this study to explain the concept of consistent learning model. To find out the relationship among variables of learning like Medium of Education, Average hours of Study, Gender and Learning capacities and the impact of Consistent Learning Model. The study is conducted in Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Mangalore. A professional college offering two

year's Master of Social Work Course which is affiliated to Mangalore University a State University in India. The data was collected through a structured questionnaire and are coded, tabulated and statistical tools like percentage, correlation and chi-square, are used. The population for the study consisted of 54 Final year HR Specialisation students during the academic year 2014-15. The study was done by using primary data and secondary data respectively. Primary data was collected by using structured questionnaire and secondary data by referring books, journals, bulletins and

internet sources. The present study adopted purposive sampling method to study 31 students who adopted consistent learning method for learning Labour Legislation subject. Among them, (83.9 per cent) are Male and (16.1 per cent) are Female. (64.5 per cent) perceived their under-graduation in Kannada Medium and rest (35.5 per cent) in English Medium. It is inferred that the students have communication problem while studying Labour legislation subject. The study comprised (71 per cent) average learners, (22.6 per cent) fast learners and (6.5 per cent) slow learners hence this study proves that ‘Pradeep Consistent Learning Model’ progressively improve learning capacity of the average and slow learners.

(a) Scope of the Study: The paper attempts to analyse the impact of different factors like Medium of education, Average hours of study, Gender and learning capacity on the effectiveness of consistent learning model for labour legislation subject in social work education. The study focus on analyzing the level of knowledge, learning attitude and skill improvement of the respondents. The model aims to progress in learning among the slow learners who are weak in recalling and analyzing the concepts. Even though implementation of this model is steady and slow but consistent learning model works as a progressive educational tool for the slow learners.

(b) Objectives of the study: To study the conceptual framework on learning; To analyze the significance of Gender, Medium of Education, Average hours and Learning capacity over learning attitude, abilities and skills. To introduce ‘Pradeep Model of Consistent Learning’ - An Innovative Pedagogy for Social Work Higher Education.

5. Merits of the Model/Evidence of Success

The present study lists the following merits of the Consistent Learning Model. Majority (45.2 per cent) respondents study 05 to 07 hours per week. (83.9 per cent) respondents reported that learning through this model has become a routine to analyze the concepts taught which improves the learning quality through understanding it. for (90.3 per cent) the method helped to face field work viva-voce examination, (93.5 per cent) the chart helps to recall the ‘key points’ to answer in the examination. (58.1 per cent) Every day reading and memorizing the ‘key points’ will improve the knowledge which increasing understanding capacity. (58.1 per cent) says the model cost worthy, (87.1 per cent) easy to adopt, (90.3 per cent) model improves consistently, (96.8 per cent) there is way for taking suggestions, (90.3 per cent) it is attractive by nature, (83.9 per cent) flexible to add information, (58.1 per cent) Filled chart will give confidence about learning by enriching the morale towards the subject, (93.5 per cent) says the method will help to imprint the labour legislation concepts into mind, (64.5 per cent) respondents rated the significance of consistent picture learning technique method as very useful, The result of this method can be analysed each day in the class through the entry test or with self test by insisting their friend to ask some questions, 96.8 per cent are curious to look at other students chart, (54.8 per cent) are using Graphs, Flowcharts, words, Figures and Number in the chart, It can be concluded that Pradeep Model consistent learning is easy and innovative pedagogy for social work higher education institutions.

6. Demerits of the Model/Problems Encountered

The students need to understand the concepts very clearly in the class itself (93.5 per cent) reported that misunderstanding

of the topic leads to wrong representation in the chart thereby, leads to learning errs. Hence, the method demands Intellectually empowered student centric Faculty/Teacher who has complete hold on the subject with efficiency and information input. Teacher should be competent guide and motivate the students for ‘Team Centric exercise’ and ‘Key Point Pedagogy’. This Model depends highly on mutual and self learning, motivation, assessment, appreciation and evaluation method. Teacher cannot compel the students to produce the chart every time in the class or it is highly difficult to supervise adoption of key point pedagogy as it is a home assignment. The study depicts that (35.5 per cent) respondents feel shy to stick the chart near to bed at post graduation education. This problem can be overcome through proper motivation. Some students may fool the teacher without enjoying the fruit of the method. This method may not be useful for the too descriptive subjects rather, suitable to subjects having equations, formulas, sections etc. There is a chance of selective learning by this method. (16.1 per cent) feel lazy to prepare the chart, (9.7 per cent) don’t have place to stick the chart, (29 per cent) says they feel difficult to adopt ‘key point pedagogy’ (19.4 per cent) cannot read every day, (19.4 per cent) other students may take the advantage of his chart (58.1 per cent) respondents forget to update the chart this is a major drawback of this method. On the hours of study the whole method depends.

7. Hypothesis Testing

The Chi-square value between Gender and Method used is found to be statistically significant ($\chi^2=8.388$) indicating that Method used in consistent learning method is dependent on the gender. Majority Male respondents used word method and female respondents used flowchart and word method. Hence it is concluded that Method used is dependent on Gender (Table 1).

Table 1: There is a significant relationship between Gender and Methods used for supplementation.

Variable	Chi-square
Gender Vs Method Used	8.388*

The Chi-square value between Learning Capacity and Understanding the concepts clearly is found to be statistically significant ($\chi^2=0.875$) indicating that the majority respondents who understood the concepts clearly are Fast learners. Average and Slow learners feel difficult in understanding the concepts clearly in the class. Hence, it can be concluded that Understanding the concepts clearly is dependent on the Learning Capacity of the respondents (Table 2).

Table 2: There is significant relationship between Learning Capacity of the respondents & Understanding the concepts in the class

Variable	Chi-square value at significance level of 0.05 per cent
Learning Capacity Vs Understanding the concept clearly	0.875*

The Chi-square value between Learning Capacity and Discussion before adopting the method is found to be statistically significant ($\chi^2=6.623$) indicating that the majority respondents who are average learners has discussed with roommates before adopting the consistent learning method. Hence, it can be concluded that the ability to discuss before adopting the method is dependent on the Learning Capacity of the respondents (Table 3).

Table 3: There is a significant relationship between learning capacity of the respondents and discussion before adopting the method.

Variable	Chi-square value at significance level of 0.05 per cent
Learning Capacity Vs Discussed before adopting the method	6.623*

The Chi-square value between Learning Capacity and Motivation to update the chart and study everyday is found to be statistically significant ($\chi^2=7.871$) indicating that the majority respondents who are average learners are motivated to update the chart and study every day. Hence, it can be concluded that the motivation to update the chart and study each day is dependent on the Learning Capacity of the respondents (Table 4).

Table 4: There is a significant relationship between Learning Capacity of the respondents & Motivation to update the chart and study every day.

Variable	Chi-square value at significance level of 0.05 per cent
Learning Capacity Vs Motivation to update and study every day.	7.871*

The Chi-square value between Medium of Education and Motivation to update the chart and study everyday is found to be statistically significant ($\chi^2=1.151$) indicating that the majority respondents who studied in Kannada Medium are motivated to update the chart and study every day. Hence, the respondents who face English communication problem are interested to study labour legislation subject by 'Pradeep consistent learning Model' hence, it can be concluded that the motivation to study every day is dependent on the Medium of Education of the respondents (Table 5).

Table 5: There is a significant relationship between Medium of Education & Motivation to and study every day.

Variable	Chi-square value at significance level of 0.05 per cent
Medium of Education Vs Motivation to study	1.151*

8. Conclusion

In a participatory method of teaching, it is assumed that knowledge and education are never neutral and the trainers role is to help the participants understand where their own views have come from, to challenge pre-conceptions and to encourage them to consider other possibilities. It assumes that society can be transformed by the engagement of critically conscious persons, through a process of deconstruction, reconstruction and transformation. Participants life experiences are the major source of knowledge in this method. The trainers are not teachers, but facilitators, and partners with the participants in this process of social change. The 'Pradeep consistence Learning Model' aims to bring up the slow learners who cannot recollect the information which they have learnt. Any concept taught in the class is converted into simplified flow charts or figures without changing the core meaning through Team Centric Exercise through mutual interaction and common understanding of the learners. Each student is guided to paste one chart sheet near to his bed and every day student should update the 'Key Points' of the labour legislations subject which may even include suplimentation by using key words, pictures, flowcharts, graphs, numbers,

formulas which are finalized in the Team even the learner can add his own views according to his reason and understanding. Student is motivated to adopt read and memorise the 'Key Points' every day the person goes to sleep. If consistently practiced this will gradually improve the learning capacity of average and slow learners and the key points of subject will be imprinted in their mind. Next day before commencing the next class an entry test is done to assess the progress. Previous days reading helps the student to answer the entry test well and thereby get appreciation in the class and also to score good class participation marks thereby to focus for maximum marks in the internal assessment. Motivation plays a vital role in this method and regular follow-up of the learning should be checked by the teacher. The teacher should guide the students for Team Centric exercise and adopting key point pedagogy. It is a mutual learning method which not only improves the analytical and memorizing capacity of the students but also improves the mentoring, supervision and follow up skills of a teacher. This method can be adopted in any institution of higher education because it is cost worthy and easy to adapt. Hence this can be considered one of the best practices in Teaching.

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